

Yashil IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
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FUNDAMENTALS OF INNOVATIVE MANAGEMENT AND ITS ORGANIZATIONAL CONTROL

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Abstract: The article describes ways to organize innovative management in the sustainable development of the economy. According to the experience of economically developed countries, new innovations are compared to the usual organizational conditions of the economy tables are used that allow you to make huge profits. In addition, it is a clear technological innovation, organizational innovations for its realization are presented.

Key words: economically developed, specific technological innovations, cycle of innovation, new technologies, scientific and technical activities, investment capital, innovative processes.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada iqtisodiyotning barqaror rivojlanishida innovatsion menejmentni tashkil etish yo'llari bayon etilgan. Iqtisodiy rivojlangan mamlakatlar tajribasiga ko'ra, yangi innovatsiyalar iqtisodiyotning odatiy tashkiliy shartlari bilan taqqoslanadi, bu sizga katta foyda olish imkonini beradi. Bundan tashqari, innovatsion menejment texnologik yangilik bo'lib, uni amalga oshirish uchun tashkiliy innovatsiyalar taqdim etish dolzarbdir.

Kalit so'zlar: iqtisodiy rivojlangan, o'ziga xos texnologik innovatsiyalar, innovatsiyalar tsikli, yangi texnologiyalar, ilmiy-texnik faoliyat, investitsion kapital, innovatsion jarayonlar.

Аннотация: В статье описаны пути организации инновационного управления в условиях устойчивого развития экономики. По опыту экономически развитых стран, новые инновации сравниваются с обычными организационными условиями экономики, используются таблицы, позволяющие получать огромные прибыли. Кроме того, это явная технологическая инновация, представлены организационные инновации для ее реализации.

Ключевые слова: экономически развитые, конкретные технологические инновации, инновационный цикл, новые технологии, научно-техническая деятельность, инвестиционный капитал, инновационные процессы.

INTRODUCTION

We know that changing the quality of products or services requires resources (energy, time, money, etc.). The process of transferring novelty (innovation) to the process of introduction (innovation) also requires various resources, the most important of which are investment and time. In the market conditions similar to the system of economic relations, the demand, supply and prices formed in the framework of the purchase and sale of goods, as the main component of innovative activity, innovation is manifested. News shapes the market, investment shapes the capital market, and innovation shapes pure competition in the market. Investment in a broad sense is understood as the use of new technologies, various products and services, organizational technical and socio-economic decisions. The process of structure, creation and dissemination of innovation is called the life cycle of innovation. News market (innovations).

It is the main product of the market and is considered a scientific and technical-resultative product of intellectual activity. It is subject to copyright and similar rights (these rights are within the framework of international, republican, corporate and other legal and regulatory acts). In world experience, there is a difference between scientific (scientific research), scientific and technical activities, and at the same time experimental (design work) discoveries. Scientific (research) activity is aimed at acquisition, distribution and application of new knowledge.

Figure 1: Scheme of investment activity

The news market forms scientific organizations, temporary scientific communities, associations of scientific workers, commercial organizations, independent scientific laboratories and departments, national and traditional news creators.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

A purely competitive market for innovation. A purely competitive market is such an association of sellers and buyers that the above does not affect current prices. The use of the concept of pure competition frees us from consideration of price, non-price, unfair and other types of competition, and at the same time, among the subjects of production relations, the distribution of capital investment in the most profitable area in such areas as the market, the source of resources, and examples of scientific and technical activity. includes fighting.

- **Capital market.** It is difficult to find an organization that does not want to grow. The household needs to buy or renew furniture, video equipment, cars, carpets. And the enterprise needs to buy technologies that can compete in foreign and domestic markets, find new markets for distribution of its products, find new suppliers and consumers. The state will need new types of weapons, environmentally friendly energy, and resource-saving technologies.
- **World associations.** We need ways to master Mars and other planets, how to use the resources of the world ocean. Modern science and technology allow us to achieve all this today. But the main limitation of all the above-mentioned needs is capital of various types (shared, circulating, shareholder, venture, chartered, etc.). The main criteria of capital market development are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Capital market in the innovation sector.

Goals and tasks, organization and control of innovative management

The ultimate goal of innovation management is to ensure the high competitiveness of innovative products and effective organization of innovative processes based on the functionalization of long-term IC (investment capital). They are the criteria for effective organization of innovative processes in the company, and are economic indicators that allow calculating the profit from the realization of an innovative product and the costs of innovative activity in modern conditions. The usefulness and profitability of IC is not considered as a goal, but as a condition and result of the implementation of innovative activities. Management ensures the effectiveness and interdependence of all internal and external elements of IC. This state of the innovative system is called harmony. Achieving harmony in IC activities is the main goal of innovative management. According to ICs, the function of harmony is divided into endogenous and exogenous directions. Endogenous harmony means coordination of all internal system elements of IC, its subsystems. In order to ensure endogenous harmony, it is necessary to develop a special system of management within the innovative company. The following tasks are solved in it:

- production of strategic innovative complete village;
- formation of innovative projects and programs and determination of thematic directions of activity;
- organization system and innovation management system development;
- planning production processes and realization of innovative products;
- selection and placement of personnel, ensuring effective use of IK potential;
- distribution of work according to the calendar and monitoring of its completion;
- creating an environment for creativity and providing intellectual work with high motivation.

Exogenous compatibility ensures the compatibility of IC with the external environment supersystems and is carried out by taking into account the limitations of the external environment and the purposeful orientation of innovative activities. Exogenous compatibility in innovation management considers the following tasks:

- formation of long-term and short-term goals of innovative activity;
- organization and conduct of marketing research;
- planning of environmental protection works and taking into account the ecological process;
- evaluation and use of advanced achievements and progressive experience of competitors;
- organization of cooperation in innovative programs;
- Taking into account objective ideas of ITT and customer requirements.

The essence of the innovation management process. The main subject functions of management determine the essence of the innovation management process and include the formation of innovation activity goals, innovation planning, organization and control of work in the production of innovation. (Chart 3).

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Formation of goals of innovative activity. The management process according to the diagram begins with the formation of goals and tasks of innovative activity in a specific period of time. In innovation management, the goal is the required or non-required (desired) state of the innovation system during the planned period, taken as a sum of all indicators. The goals of the organization or activity must have a clear direction in a certain period of time. Thus, the organizational goal, on the one hand, is the result of process evaluation and forecasting, and on the other hand, it serves as a boundary for planned innovative activities. In order to fulfill these two functions, the formation of the innovation goal must meet several requirements. The main ones include:

1. The goal of innovation should have a clear form and be measurable. They can be scientific, technical, economic, social or political in nature, and they are aimed at solving production, finance, personnel, marketing tasks of development. However, when forming the goals of all innovative activities, they should have a clear view, correspond to the description of the type of innovation, and determine the internal and external directions of the organization.
2. The goals of the innovation should be distributed according to the exact time to achieve the desired results. The direction of goals in time makes it possible to clarify the ways, methods of achieving them, to divide them into periods, to ensure the continuous development of the organization.

3. It should be possible to achieve innovation goals. A strategy for achieving the goal is developed to prepare a program of planned activities for the realization of the adopted development strategy. Therefore, the goals of innovative activity should be a task that can be achieved.
4. Different goals of innovation are related to each other and should not contradict each other. A preferred innovation is the form of the organization's goals system, which is understood to be a tree view of its goals.

Figure 3: The relationship between the main functions of innovation management

The process of forming goals is one of the important measures of innovation management. It is the main part and primary point of all planning calculations in the field of innovation.

Organization of innovations (Chart 4.). The organizational essence function includes solving planned tasks for the implementation of the adopted IC development strategy. For this, it is necessary to determine the amount of necessary resources, allocate issues, determine the time of the executors, determine the cooperation of the participants, ensure control and do other things. The organization of innovations, which occupies a significant part of the activities of managers at all levels, is one of the main functions of innovation management. Organization in innovation management ensures the appropriate unity of all elements of the innovation process in terms of time and space in order to effectively implement the adopted planning decisions, the tasks, forms and methods of creating organizational decisions are understood as important signs of systematization and diversification of the organization of innovation.

Forms of organization of innovative processes		
Organizational tasks	Forms of organization	Methods of organization
In space	specialized	formal
at the time	concentrated	informal
	cooperated	
	combined	

Figure 4: Forms of organization of innovation

Different forms of organization of innovation are used in innovation management. The term “structure form” refers to the combination of elements of innovation processes in space and time and methods of operation. In terms of content, innovation structure forms consist of different methods of division of labor in carrying out innovation projects. Such organizational forms of innovation can include concentration, specialization, cooperation and combinations.

CONCLUSION

In short, the review of the main functions of innovation management and the procedure for their implementation form the general technological system of innovation management. They are equally important in both strategic and operational spheres of management. Each pair of connected subject functions reflects the appearance of self-contained management decisions operating in the “goal-factor” period. The organization of innovation management can be controlled through the innovation activity scheme of innovation infrastructures, the connection between the main functions of innovation management and the organization of innovation processes.

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